

ACT4CAP27

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Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

This is the 1st newsletter of the ACT4CAP27 project WHERE YOU CAN:

- Find out what ACT4CAP27 is all about
- Read about the latest developments of the project
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is ACT4CAP27?

ACT4CAP27 is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action, aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027.

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Dear ACT4CAP27 Community,

As ACT4CAP27 approaches its 10th month this December, we take a moment to reflect on the progress we've made together in our mission to enhance the European agricultural sector's resilience and sustainability.

Our project aims to equip EU policymakers with advanced tools, models, and evidence-based strategies to address future challenges and opportunities in the evolving agri-food landscape, ensuring that EU agricultural policies are both forward-thinking and responsive to global and regional needs.

This year's journey in March began with our kickoff meeting in The Hague, where we laid the groundwork for a collaborative approach to policy innovation. In October, our project was also introduced to EC officers in a Brussels workshop of Horizon funded projects clustering in the topic of models and tools supporting agriculture policies

One of the defining aspects of ACT4CAP27 is our commitment to stakeholder engagement. This was exemplified during our 1st Stakeholder Meeting in Brussels, where policymakers, representatives of industry, NGOs, farmers organisations and researchers convened to provide insights and shape the project's direction. These collaborative efforts ensure that ACT4CAP27's outcomes are grounded in practical realities and tailored to the diverse needs of the agricultural community.

Our presence at international conferences (EAAE Seminars, AIEEA Conference) showcased our project's commitment to fostering resilient agricultural systems. Participation in the OECD Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Productivity to Address Food Systems Challenges in Paris highlighted our contributions to critical global discussions on climate adaptation, economic sustainability, and agricultural innovation.

Our collaboration with fellow Horizon Europe projects, such as BrightSpace, underscores our commitment to fostering cross-project synergies, enhancing our collective impact on future EU agricultural policies.

Looking ahead, 2025 promises to be a pivotal year. Our Annual Meeting, scheduled for February in Rome, will be a valuable opportunity to review our progress, refine our strategies, and strengthen our partnerships.

As you delve into this newsletter, we invite you to explore the latest developments, insights, and visions that have shaped the ACT4CAP27 project throughout its first 10 months. Your continued support and engagement have been instrumental in our journey so far, and we are excited about the milestones that await us in the year to come.

Thank you for being an integral part of the ACT4CAP27 community.

Wishing you a peaceful festive season and all the best for the new year ahead.

Warm regards,

Siemen van Berkum

ACT4CAP27 Project Coordinator, on behalf of the ACT4CAP27 team

Meet the ACT4CAP27 project team

The consortium of ACT4CAP27 consists of 13 partners from 10 countries in Europe (AT, BE, DE, IT, HU, NL, ES, SE, UA, UK), and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission.

The partners bring in expertise from modelling across different ecoclimatic conditions and socio-economic realities within Europe. The consortium includes partners from the private and public sector representing:

- (a) Academia and higher education (PNU, SLU, UCL, UPM, UNIROMA3, WU);
- (b) SMEs dealing with research consultancy, data collection, and model development (EuroCARE), SMEs with a strong track record in the field of communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation (POS, ECORYS);
- (c) Public government bodies and international research institutes dealing with agricultural and environmental research, data collection and, building agricultural models at different scales (WR, Thünen, IIASA).

[Read more »](#)

Group photo at the Kick-off Meeting, 18-19 March, 2024, The Hague

Specific Objectives

-
1. DESIGNING & operationalize a conceptual data and modelling framework
-
2. Better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and ASSESSING policy impact.
-
3. Developing an enhanced modular MODELLING Toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals.
-
4. SAFEGUARDING the uptake and update of the integrated and modular toolbox and community building.
-
5.PLATFORM for stakeholder interaction and dialogues – at different stages of the project

Project structure

The ACT4CAP27 project is managed through 8 work packages (WP), each of which oversees and/or are responsible for various parts of the five-year project. [Read more »](#)

Latest news from ACT4CAP27

1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project 23 October 2024, Brussels BE

The first stakeholder meeting organized by Ecorys brought together policymakers, researchers, and key stakeholders of the agri-food industry to discuss strategies for achieving sustainable EU food systems.

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Read our Policy Brief

ACT4CAP27 has released its first Policy Brief, addressing the urgent need for advanced tools to guide the post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform. The brief highlights the challenges of incorporating sustainability, equity, and resilience into CAP reforms...

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ACT4CAP27 at OECD Conference, 28 October 2024, Paris, FR

Possessio was representing the ACT4CAP27 consortium at the Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Productivity to Address Food Systems Challenges: Measurement, Data, Drivers and Policies organized on 28 October 2024 in Paris.

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ACT4CAP27 Kick-off in The Hague

13 partners from 10 European countries came together in the Hague on 18 March 2024 to mark the start of the 5-year research project ACT4CAP27.

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ACT4CAP27 Highlights from Ukraine

ACT4CAP27 presented at
Horizon Europe Cluster 6 information day
30 October 2024, Polissia National University, Zhytomyr, UA

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ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon Europe Cluster 6 information day in Ukraine

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eaae 189th EAAE Seminar
EU enlargement by (post-)war Ukraine:
Implications for the Agri-Food Markets

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WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship
18 September 2024, Warsaw, PL

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Communication events

ACT4CAP27 Presented at the
65th Annual Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics

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ACT4CAP27 Presented at the 65th Annual SIE Meeting, Urbino, IT

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eaae 188th EAAE Seminar
Reorienting agri-food chains to hinder climate change and food security threats

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ACT4CAP27 represented at 188th EAAE Seminar by Thünen team

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Roma Tre University ACT4CAP27 Team presented
"Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry"

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Roma Tre University ACT4CAP27 Team presentation at AIEAA Conference

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ACT4CAP27 at the Joint Workshop of European Association of Wine Economists

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Networking and Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon projects' Clustering Workshop

[Read more »](#)

ACT4CAP27 Collaborates with BrightSpace

[Read more »](#)

Further highlights from our fellow projects

- Press Release: BrightSpace Project Annual Meeting, 5-6 November 2024 [Read more »](#)
- BrightSpace public deliverables [Read more »](#)
- Open Access Article in Nature Food [Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE

- Inventory of existing methods and tools used for the design, implementation and monitoring of CAP Strategic Plans [Read more »](#)
- TOOLS4CAP public deliverables [Read more »](#)
- TOOLS4CAP Academy [Read more »](#)

TOOLS₄CAP

Upcoming events

- [EU Agri-Food Days, 10-12 December 2024, Brussels, BE](#)
- [191th EAAE Seminar, 10-14 February 2025, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, DE](#)
- [ACT4CAP27 Annual Meeting, 24-25 February 2025, Rome, IT](#)
- [FFA Conference, 1 April 2025, Brussels, BE](#)
- [2025 AES Conference, 14-16 April 2025, Bordeaux, FR](#)
- [ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025, 23-27 June 2025 Vienna, AT](#)
- [2025 EAAE Congress, 26-29 August 2025, Bonn, DE](#)

ACT4CAP27

More information will be sent in our next ACT4CAP27 newsletter scheduled for spring 2025.

Thank you for signing up to the [ACT4CAP27 newsletters](#).

Further information can be found on the ACT4CAP27 project homepage:

<https://act4cap27.eu/>

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PARTNERS

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